

Leadership Competencies for Librarians

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ABSTRACT

The development of informational infrastructure of a library is done, keeping in view the user's requirements. The responsibilities, duties and skills to manage resources, services and personnel, determine the leadership competency of librarians. In current technologically advanced information age, the role of librarians becomes more important and challenging, as they are expected to develop and manage hybrid libraries, following user-centric approach. Considering the management of varied informational needs of patrons and emerging technologies in libraries, there is a great demand of skilled library professionals. This has been observed that current trend of library science practices in India moving the professionals towards steeped managerialism instead of dynamic leadership. Such approaches disallow the professionals to be more innovative, creative and culturally effective leaders. The current article identifies and addresses some of the potentials required for librarians to convert them from managers to leaders. The article aims to inspire young library professionals to transform themselves with help of managerial traits and succeed professionally.

Keywords: Library leadership, leadership among librarians, effective library leaders, leadership competency.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Libraries are service oriented agencies, sincerely meant to serve the community and librarianship is to enrich, enlighten and empower the society with information both nascent and retrospective. Librarians shoulder multiple responsibilities of acquiring, organizing and disseminating information to its esteemed users. They have to understand and interpret an increasingly complex information environment. For this, they have to be excellent managers capable of innovation, initiative and strong leadership qualities to fulfil the ever increasing and challenging information needs of the users. Modern librarians need to have a multifaceted personality, a conglomeration of various traits like professional competence, vision, high ethical standards, sense of responsibility, initiative, impressive communication skills, humility and a sympathetic attitude. "Librarians must accept and adapt to the new techniques and systems. They must recognize the enormous potential of the virtual library, address the issues involved in its creation, and take a leadership role in integrating these new systems and services into libraries" (Sarasvathy, Namratha, Giddaiah, 2012)

The recent technological advancements have greatly influenced library services and resources. The role of librarians nowadays is more challenging than before as they need to cater the varied

information needs of clients. The Information Technology revolution and greater availability of online contents has further expanded the information explosion, creating a demand for more functionalities of a library. This has been observed that from the last one decade librarians are striving hard to manage library collections. In such scenario the role of information manager/librarian becomes more important as he has to lead from front and take responsibility to provide best services to the users by all means.

Johnson (2007) states that "librarians and other information professionals need to take a leadership role in ensuring that their communities can make the best possible use of these resources and thus contribute to the social and economic advancement of their people." Librarian as a profession requires leadership and skills to manage staff, collection, resources and services. "Demonstrating leadership means being able to influence and lead a group of diverse individuals to attain common goals and objectives. It differs from management, which normally involves a defined skill set and a position with supervisory responsibilities" (Feldmann, Level, and Liu 2013).

This paper defines leadership skills and qualities that are essential for knowledge managers/librarians. The significance of leadership in libraries has been highlighted with certain characteristics that the librarians should necessarily possess. The paper also dwells on ethics for librarians and the leadership qualities for present and future library leaders.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

There is a distinction between various terminology used for leadership competency, traits and characteristics. Various authors have discussed and explained the term 'leadership competency' on the basis their own personal experiences and earlier studies. Nearly all of them adjudged the term 'leadership' as knowledge, skills and abilities attained by a leader.

Needham (2001) stresses upon several important leadership roles to be played by librarians in creating an environment to nurture a successful transition of libraries. All these roles will help to create standards and protocols for library profession and further be used for advocacy, mentoring, creating heroes, and also to underwrite leadership training for new members of the profession.

Unaeye (2003) focuses on the dynamics of leadership and management of academic library reference services and what is expected of the reference department head of the 21st century. His study explores the changing roles of reference librarians and those of their leaders or department heads. It examines the leadership skills, traits, and competencies and attributes expected of the department head of reference in the new millennium.

Arora (2004) highlighted leadership skills and personal traits that were used successfully for transforming a traditional library into a hybrid library in precarious circumstances and conditions that exist in some of the organizations in India. It describes the management techniques, skills and personal traits of a leader that were used to motivate staff members to computerize the library, to improve library services and to transform a traditional library into a hybrid library.

Winston (2005) addressed the issue of leadership competencies as a part of defining the nature of effective leadership, the leadership qualities and areas of knowledge needed by those who contribute to organizational success, and the educational preparation needed by leaders.

Pors (2008) conducted leadership survey in Denmark based on extensive interviewing of directors and staff members from 24 public libraries. The main findings supports some of the newer theoretical literature concerned with isomorphism, translation and diffusion of standards and recipes, namely that the variation is great and that some of the processes are heavily influenced by the organizational culture in which leadership plays an important role.

Fitsimmons (2009) discussed that managing skill sets in practicing the performance standard of managing people effectively and results found that individuals are more productive when they have the chance to use their unique skill sets rather than having to do tasks for which they have little or no skills simply because those tasks are part of a larger function.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study aims to;

- Understand the concept of leadership in the preview of librarianship;
- Know leadership traits practiced in libraries;
- Define leadership competency for librarians;
- Explore certain ethics and leadership qualities for librarians.

4. LEADERSHIP DEFINED

Every individual has his own perspective about 'Leadership', which is based on his personal experiences, observations and learning in life. The leadership defined in literature is significantly influenced by the historical figures who defined a set of traits owned by leaders. The different point of view about the meaning of leadership depends upon the nature of leadership.

Bolden (2004) in his research report on "What is leadership?" states that the topic of leadership has been of interest for many hundreds of years, from the early Greek philosophers such as Plato and Socrates to the plethora of management and leadership gurus, whose books fill airport bookshops. It is argued that in this changing, global environment, leadership holds the answer not only to the success of individuals and organisations, but also to sectors, regions and nations.

Northouse (2004) identified four common themes in the way leadership now tends to be conceived: (1) leadership is a process; (2) leadership involves influence; (3) leadership occurs in a group context; and (4) leadership involves goal attainment. He thus defines leadership as "a process whereby an individual influences a group of individuals to achieve a common goal".

Despite recognition of the importance of leadership, however, there remains a certain mystery as to what leadership actually is or how to define it. In a review of leadership research, Stogdill (1974) concluded that there are "almost as many definitions of leadership as there are persons who have attempted to define the concept".

In a nutshell we can believe that leadership is a multifaceted phenomenon that redefines its meaning keeping in view the organization's or individual's goals. The characteristics of leadership also depends upon the social structure and its' influence and motivation. "...leadership is like the Abominable Snowman, whose footprints are everywhere but who is nowhere to be seen." (Bennis and Nanus, 1985)

Good leaders are followed mainly because people trust and respect them for their leadership qualities (<http://ezinearticles.com/>). Good looks, height are not necessary to become a leader, but to be vocal having a tremendous convincing power to get the works done are positively necessary for a good leaders, The diagram given below illustrates some of the characteristics of effective leadership;

Figure 1: Characteristics of effective leadership skills for librarians

Many scholars view leadership as a product of the situation. A person with particular qualities or traits that a situation requires emerges as a leader. Good leaders recognize the needs of the subordinates and help them to overcome the obstacles in satisfying those needs. A leader influences other's behaviour by his charisma and concern.

5. LEADERSHIP IN LIBRARIES

The Leadership in libraries plays an important role in providing effective library service to the clients. The Library manager/librarian has to be scholar, good leader and a cultured human being who is sympathetic and concerned towards the staff and patron's needs. Library work is a team work and librarian has the responsibility to bring about proper coordination among various sections to achieve the prime objectives, i.e. users' satisfaction. Leadership should be legitimately exercised at multiple levels by staff in a library. The MortensonCenter report(2004) recommends active participation of library professionals in library leadership programs to:

- Nurture and educate future library administrators and ICT library leaders
- Maintain exposure to emerging best practices within the profession
- Develop leadership skills
- Encourage partnerships across national boundaries.

The above developments have huge implications for library management; strategy formulation, staff development, organizational culture and most importantly change management. But it has to be led

by individuals who recognize it as a reinvigorate practice of librarianship. The revived practice of librarianship will bring following outcomes:

- A self-sustaining independent library leadership centre;
- Well designed comprehensive library leadership plan;
- High level of measurable improved skills;
- Developed cadre of well trained library leaders;
- A team of library trainers;
- User-centric enriched document collection;
- Electronic library contents, shared by many users at a time;
- Higher level of satisfaction among staff and patrons.

The libraries should be focused on introduction to Web technologies; dynamic librarianship; bringing the best in library management; leadership development; improved communication & interpersonal skills; user's need management; ethics & leadership; reconciliation and cultural integration in the workplace; knowledge management; competitive intelligence; marketing and branding of information products; discussion of application of recent trends in libraries etc. Most importantly the networking within the libraries should be strengthened. Keeping in view the above constraints, library leaders have significant role to play in future development of libraries.

6. LEADERSHIP COMPETENCY

The concept of leadership competency was adopted as a basis for management education and development in the UK following the Review of Vocational Qualifications report in 1986 (De Ville, 1986) and continues to be widely promoted. "From a review of 26 leadership and management frameworks in use throughout the public and private sectors Bolden et al.(2003) concluded that a somewhat moderated version of transformational leadership (Bass, 1985; Bass and Avolio, 1994) tends to be promoted in most frameworks".

The notion of 'leadership competency' is squeezed through the churning of historical theories and traits that could not make a mutual consensus on defining the leadership. Leadership competency is defined as a set of leadership characteristics and standards that are needed to acquire by an individual/s for the overall development of organization. With the growing approaches in leadership excellence, the assessment of leadership competency has become a fast emerging area in the field of management studies and research.

Leadership competency, therefore, is conceived as a set of values, qualities and behaviours exhibited by the leader that encourage the participation, development, and commitment of followers. Leadership is also considered as the art of influencing an individual or individuals in a particular direction which involves casting vision, goal setting and motivating people (Spendlove 2007).

6.1 LEADERSHIP COMPETENCY FOR LIBRARIANS

In an academic environments leadership is defined as "a process of social influence in which a person can enlist the aid and support of others in the accomplishment of a common task" (Chmers, 1997).

The changing nature of work is significantly influencing the role of librarians in all types of libraries. The behavioural changes of users and inclusion of varied informational sources and services are

increasing pressure on library administration to establish or introduce dynamic modern libraries with collaboration and partnerships.

Besides core qualities of a librarian as a leader/manager, leadership competency is required to exhibit more skills to adapt to the changing informational environment over the time. The emerging characteristics of a librarian include; openness, apathy, integrity, and awareness of recent development in his own field. He is also desired to create such an environment where his colleagues demand more participation and take responsibility of every given task. A librarian is a good leader if he/she possesses following leadership qualities:

- **Technical and professional competence**

A true librarian should have professional and technical competence to influence and motivate others. He/she should at any time be aware of the latest developments in the field and should have command over different library concepts. So that he is able to provide right direction to the staff. For every problem or doubt the staff members seek guidance from the librarian.

- **Sense of responsibility**

A librarian should have a high sense of responsibility and self restraint. His/her personal problems, issues, biases' should not affect his/her decision making for the day to day functioning of the library.

- **Vision**

Vision is indispensable for the overall growth and progress of the library. A librarian should necessarily be a strong visionary to bring about innovations in library services.

- **Enthusiasm**

A librarian should be committed and enthusiastic to take initiative in all tasks that are essential to achieve the organization's goals. The staff members will automatically put in their best efforts and interest if the librarian is highly committed and enthusiastic professional.

- **Communication skills**

A librarian should necessarily have excellent communication skills. Effective and impressive communication is an asset for a successful librarian. The librarian should also be a good listener and welcome views, emotions and prejudices while making decisions.

- **Flexibility**

The librarian should not have a rigid outlook to perceive things as no two situations and persons are similar. He/she has to adapt himself in handling different situations and people, thus successfully manage stress and induce a harmonious and congenial work environment.

- **High ethical standards**

Ethics play a great role in librarianship, as they are strong foundations of all professional activities and decision making. Professional ethics require a librarian to be a role model for the staff members.

The true mark of leadership in a librarian is good vision for his/her library, motivating others to share and accomplish that vision. One cannot be a leader, and ask others to follow him, unless he himself knows how to follow too. No matter what leadership position is held by that person but there is still someone to whom he has to respond to.

6.2 ETHICS FOR LIBRARIANS

Librarians must sincerely follow professional ethics to become good library managers. Some of the professional ethics expected from librarians are;

- To perform duties in accordance with the known expectations and needs of the users of his library.
- To not to discriminate between or against library users/staff.
- To respect the confidentiality of each library user.
- To honour the freedom of libraries in collecting and preserving library materials.
- To actively participate in the formulation of policy in the operation and services of his library.
- To cooperate and work with other librarians in efforts to develop professional competencies.
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6.3 LEADERSHIP QUALITIES FOR FUTURE LIBRARY LEADERS

The growth and development of future libraries are shouldered on librarians who possess the passion and enthusiasm to be a true leader. Following is an outline of traits that future librarians should have:

- **Physical**

Librarians should be energetic and should calmly tolerate, stress and never show concern about being overworked.

- **Emotional**

Librarians should have high level of self confidence to attempt challenging tasks. They should always have a desire to improve and understand own strengths and weaknesses. Librarians should not dwell on mistakes but view them as opportunities to learn and move on. Strong librarians should be courageous, ambitious, and confident to take risks and always ready to accept responsibilities. Librarians have to be humble and exhibit concern for others in their times of doubt and problems.

- **Social**

Librarians should be trustworthy, keep promises and fulfil responsibilities. They should listen, motivate, empower others and take initiative in social situations. He should be socially active and must converse with staff and patrons time to time to upgrade the library services and resources.

- **Intellectual/Intelligence**

A true library leader learns from experience and adapts to change. He has to possess extensive knowledge to provide good judgement, effective planning and impressive problem solving capability. The mantra for success of a responsible librarian is to never react right away, but to consider the situation and suspend judgement until all the facts are put in.

- **Communication**

Good communication skills are essential for a librarian to get followers aligned behind the goals of the library. Librarian should be expert in one-to-one communication, excellent writing skills and of course a superior speaker.

- **Experience**

Successful librarians need to be scholars and experienced in a variety of situations where they must have skills and expertise in dealing with different types of problems. The librarians have to be skilled in performing tasks and should have ability to mentor those who follow them.

- **Trustworthy**

Librarians have to be sympathetic, caring genuinely about the well being of their staff and users so that the staff/users have strong confidence and belief that their leader will support, defend and always stand by them.

6.4 LEADERSHIP QUALITIES TO BUILD COMPETENCY AMONG LIBRARIANS

A good library leader must have the discipline to work towards his/her vision single handily, as well as to direct his/her actions and those of his team towards the goal. The librarian always indulged in creative activities, inspires others to do the same. A true library leader should possess the following qualities;

- **Integrity**

Integrity is the combination of outer actions and inner values. A person of integrity doesn't practice double standards. A library leader must have the trust and faith of the followers and therefore must display integrity.

- **Dedication**

Dedication means making all efforts to accomplish the task at hand. By setting an excellent example, library leaders can show staff the opportunities to achieve the set goals and targets.

- **Magnanimity**

Magnanimity means giving the credit to the performer. A magnanimous library leader makes sure that the credit for successful task is duly given to the followers. This certainly enhances the efficiency of people

- **Humility**

A humble library leader always equates himself with other members of the team. Leaders with modesty understand that their status does not make them a hero.

- **Openness**

Openness means being able to welcome new ideas and accept them even if they do not conform to usual way of thinking. Openness brings mutual trust and understanding between librarian and staff.

- **Creativity**

Creativity is the ability to think differently and innovating new ideas and practices. Creativity enables library leaders to see things that others fail to see and thus lead followers to conquer new heights.

- **Fairness**

Fairness means dealing with others consistently and fairly. A librarian must understand all aspects of an issue before giving judgment. When people feel that they are being treated fairly, they reward the leader with reliability and allegiance.

- **Assertiveness**

Assertiveness is the ability to put one's point strongly. A librarian must be assertive to get the desired results. Assertiveness brings along responsibility to clearly understand what the staff expect from their library leaders.

- **Sense of humour**

Sense of humour is vital to relieve stress and boredom to keep the followers in high spirits. Effective library leaders know how to use humour to energize followers. Humour ensures happy interpersonal relations thus elevating the efficiency to do the work.

7. CONCLUSION

Moving ahead, it is without doubt, leadership competency among librarians will remain centre of importance for academic institutions. The current article outlines that leadership plays significant role in libraries where group work and team spirit is always required. The leadership skills among librarians inspire other staff members to alter their nature of work in a positive way and also to acquire strong professional skills. The study has also tried to discuss leadership competency and leadership skills required for librarians, as they need dealing with various strategic and managerial issues dealing with overall development of library and human resources. An argument is also promoted that a librarian should have leadership competencies with a reference to 'Great librarians are ones who care about the people around them'. Leadership must be based on goodwill. It is also true that much can be done to improve the leadership skills of librarians. Strong and committed leadership in libraries is indispensable for accomplishing the common target of serving the users, as the library's in-house activities are inter related to each functional unit of the library.

As librarians, we have the opportunity to re-shape the future of our profession by re-conceptualizing the institutional mission, articulating a vision and forging the alliances necessary to achieve the kind of change that is required to serve the users with utmost care and diligence. We urge to academic institutions to grant more freedom to librarians to conduct leadership practice to pay more attention towards over all development of library. It is important for librarians to interact personally and socially with users and staff on regular basis to build good library culture. The change and challenge can directly be seen for librarians and it is the need of hour to guide budding librarians to enhance their leadership/managerial skills for creating better work environment. To conclude, "the leadership journey is a never ending one. Change is a constant. Where the journey and the constant come together true leaders flourish." (IWM Syndicate Group, 2001)

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